

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14296544

Organisational Climate And Employee Satisfaction In Pharmaceutical Firms In South-East, Nigeria

Agu Cyril Obiora; Prof Anthonia Onuorah; Dr. Emeka Arinze & Dr. Dike Goodfaith Nnenna

**Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria
E-mail:agu.cyril4life@gmail.com;anthoniaonuorah34@gmail.com; emyarinze@gmail.com
and dikegoodfaith@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

The study aimed at investigating the effect of organizational climate on employees' satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were; to determine the extent to which communication affects employee satisfaction; to evaluate the effect of leadership style on employee satisfaction; to examine how organizational structure affects employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. Relevant literature on organizational climate and employee satisfaction were reviewed under conceptual review, theoretical framework, and empirical review. The research work was anchored on Person–Environment Fit Theory. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 2087. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973), was employed to arrive at a sample size of 400. The population used in the analysis was 350. Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method was used in testing the hypotheses. The result of the hypotheses showed that communication had a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. Leadership style had a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. Organisational structure had a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study concluded that organizational climate had a significant positive effect on employees' satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study recommended that management of pharmaceutical firms should provide the right tools for their employees to communicate effectively such as instant message platforms, be open and transparent, organize team-building activities and facilitate frequent feedback.

Keywords: organizational climate, employee satisfaction, pharmaceutical firms

INTRODUCTION

The trending changes in the global world has made businesses to struggle for survival or acquire sustainable competitive advantage and this has made organisations to understand the factors that influences employee's behaviour which produced a great deal of interest in investigating employee perceptions of climate within the organization. Climate or atmosphere in workplace has ire impact on employee's motivation, behaviour, attitudes and potential, which, in turn is

predicted to influence organizational productivity (Arya & Sainy, 2017). Human resource of any organization is considered as the most vital source which affects the performance of an organization because it is the only resource which can use all other resources to achieve organizational objectives and this has become an important resource affecting the satisfaction of the employees (Gosain & Sinha, 2021).

It has been extensively contended that an organisation that has goals to achieve would require satisfied and happy staff in her workforce. The achievement of set objectives and goals by any organisation is deeply rooted in her capacity to attract and retain competent and fulfilled staff into its employment (Obiukwu & Alaneme, 2017). There has been accumulative awareness on the relationship between management and employees, attitudes of the employees towards their firms, as a result of their work environment, has been a contemporary issue since 1930s. This has made organizational climate an important topic in order to understand employee's work-related behavior and has been discussed in organizational behavior literature since late 1960s (Berberoglu, 2018). Many organisations ignore organisational climate, therefore, employees' work engagement and effectiveness might be very low (Rožman & Štrukelj, 2021).

The concept of organizational climate and its implications on employee satisfaction was formally introduced by the human relationists in the late 1940s. Today, it has become a very useful metaphor for describing the social system in the workplace (Aminu, 2020). The study of an organization's climate is needed to gain insight into critical dimensions such as communication, organizational structure, leadership style, conflict management, reward strategies, physical environment, teamwork, innovation, employee satisfaction, morale, and so on. If there is two-way communication, conducive working environment, appropriate leadership styles, steps in conflict resolution, assigning of rewards/ bonuses as at when due and workers are cooperative and have a positive view of the company, the organization would be more efficient because that is the key to increasing employee performance within the organization as human capital and is by far the most valuable asset that can sustain an organization's long-term viability. (Banureka, et al, 2021). It has been shown that the three main sources that influence the effectiveness of a person's performance in an organization are; individual factors, organizational factors and environmental factors which include organizational climate and it is very important because organizations that can create an environment where employees feel friendly can reach their full potential in seeing the key to competitive advantage (Wirawan, et al, 2021). Pharmaceutical firms are one of the major drivers in the health sector of any country across the world..Pharmaceutical firms rely heavily on their employees for success to create and provide quality services to the customer. Being in the manufacturing industry, the ability of pharmaceutical firms to survive and compete is solely dependent on the quality of their services. The activities pharmaceutical sector engage in, such as blending, granulation, milling, coating, table pressing, filling and other needs, and their variety of job roles that range from laboratory-based research and development, clinical trials, regulatory affairs, drug safety, manufacturing, engineering, quality assurance, quality control, validation all the way through to marketing, sales and distribution requires management to possess the pre-requisite skills in leading the employees. This will ensure a positive organizational climate i.e. friendly and good working environment that enhances employee satisfaction because employee job satisfaction is essential for high-quality work. Employees have been seen as the dire backbone of any organization upon which the failure and success of business is dependent on their performance. Despite the number of studies, little empirical studies exist on organizational climate and employees' satisfaction in pharmaceutical industry especially in a developing country like Nigeria. There is therefore the need to explore the relationship between organizational climate and employees performance since the success or failure of any organisations depends solely on happy, satisfied and committed the employees are.

Statement of the Problem

Pharmaceutical companies face complex issues that grow more challenging by the day such as healthcare reform and changes in technology, government policy, and consumer expectations are revolutionizing relationships with key stakeholders and impacting operations in unforeseen ways. With the rising global competition, advancing technology, and the changing nature of work, organizations are required to be able to retain employees so that the goals they want are not hampered. Over the last decades, it has been observed that the devotion of an employee towards job is getting lesser day by day. Even the complaints regarding organizational climate which includes organizational processes has escalated in number. As competition is heating up, organizations are changing and taking different steps to attract and retain expertise for future success, but control on talented manpower is not enough to fight the fierce battle of tough competition in the market. This has made it a dicey situation and a difficult challenge in front of human resource manager.

As these challenges are not specific to any particular organization. Most organizations irrespective of their structure and size strive to cope with these challenges. Pharmaceutical firms are faced with challenges such a talent shortage, lack of communication, poor organisational structure, poor reward policies, unconducive work environment, poor conflict resolution, work life balance, managing diverse work force, innovative supple work patterns that boost employees performance and these contextual factors, may lead to low productivity and perhaps high employee turnover intention, and low commitment of employees. The relationship between organizational climate and achieving results has become more integrated. Fostering a positive climate is no longer an attractive choice but rather has become imperative. Employee satisfaction and organizational climate are crucial to the organisation success, particularly in the pharmaceutical industry in Nigeria. Effective strategies have been developed to curb shortcomings of the survival of pharmaceutical industries in Nigeria. Pharmaceutical industries in recent times are still faced with all these challenges. It is against this backdrop that the study will examine organizational climate and employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this research is to examine the effect of organizational climate on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. In order to achieve this, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the extent to which communication affects employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.
2. Evaluate the effect of leadership style on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.
3. Examine how organizational structure affects employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to achieve the objectives of the study:

1. To what extent does communication affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?
2. To what degree does leadership style affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?
3. To what extent does Organisational Structure affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

Hoi: Communication has no significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Hiii: Leadership style has no significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Hiiii: Organisational structure has no significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Organisational Climate

Several researchers have provided a comprehensive definitions of the term 'organisational climate'. Organisational climate can be said to be the whole of recognitions focused around the collaboration between the individual perception and organisational environment (Arya & Sainy, 2017). Grodzicki, and Kłusek-Wojciszke (2018) maintained that the climate concerns both the attributes of the organization and the perception of the individual, and that it is simply an alternative to affective reactions to the organization, such as job satisfaction. Organizational climate is seen as the mutual perceptions of, and interpretations attached to the policies, practices, and procedures experienced by the employees, as well as the behaviors they observe as being expected, supported and rewarded (Halfdensen, 2022). Positive organizational climate in workplace has impacted on employee's motivation, behaviour, attitudes and potential, which, in turn is predicted to influence organizational productivity and employees are engaged when organizations have healthy work culture and communication practices, where they can get platforms to express their concerns and opportunities to grow and develop their potential. Suari, Agung & Widyani (2022) perceive organizational climate as the perception of organizational members (individually and in groups) and those in contact with the organization (suppliers, customers, consultants, and contractors) about what is or is happening in the organization's internal environment on a regular basis, which influences organizational attitudes and behavior. Employees perceive work environment as favourable when benefits, resources and workload are reasonable and fair, equitable and mutual respect between employers and employees which culminates in steady, beneficial work outcomes and attitude. It is therefore important that managers must understand diverse work procedures that arouse staff needs and ways they can be inspired for better performance on the job.

Communication

Communication is a multidimensional concept. Communication factors responsible for employee's job satisfaction are role expectations, social support, leadership and justice (Alomi, et al, 2019). Communication is a process of meaningful and understandable transfer of ideas, thoughts and feelings among people and for communication to be successful, it is necessary for the recipient to understand the meaning of the message and show it through expected reactions (Djordjevic, et al, 2021). Communication involves informing, organizing, coordinating, arranging, and subordinating, transmission of verbal and non-verbal message and it involves a sender, a channel of communication, and a receiver by seeking understanding of other parties, and completing a process with a consistent follow-through. These things are important for building trust and satisfaction among all parties (Pongton & Suntrayuth, 2019). Effective management is based on open communication and supportiveness, candor, warmth, and a commitment to dialogue rather than monologue. Effective communication is also a key element of business success. Many research findings have suggested that effective management of the communication process brings large-scale organizational benefits. Effective communication can create a win-win when employees get feedback on their work performance as soon as possible. Chitrao (2014) in Muhammad, et al (2019) explained that a positive and good communication can increase job satisfaction and reduce complaints by the employee. Ineffective communication can lead to misunderstandings, lack of information, laziness, and more job rotation. Ineffectiveness of managers in communicating with its employees would cause an employee being unsatisfied. Thus, this situation may cause workers' job satisfaction to be affected.

Similarly, if employees do not trust the manager, then the flow of information submitted does not occur and leads to decreased job satisfaction. The leader can lead, build trust, and encourage continuous learning and inspire workers through effective communication. Therefore, managers and employees must work together to understand the principles of effective communication and communication barriers in the workplace to achieve the desired goals of the organization. Managers require extensive knowledge of communication to be efficient and effective towards their workers. Moreover, effective communication is considered as the capability of motivating and knowing how to exchange information in a group or individual and knowing the right time to communicate.

Organisational Structure

Shabbir (2019) views organizational structure as the setting up a structure or mending an already existing one to suit the organizational environment and the demands of technology. Organizational structure is the functional framework, aligning resources with defined organizational objectives in the business strategy and embodying the organization's culture that directly impacts the company's capability to attract, engage and retain employees (Nosike, Okoye & Afodigbueokwu, 2021). Organizational structure is a set of strategies for dividing an organization into discrete jobs and then achieving a balance between various responsibilities, employment positions, their interrelationships, and accountability for process and sub process outputs a formal system of task and reporting relationships that manages, directs, and motivates personnel to work together to achieve an organization's goal (Ezejiofor & Ezekwesili, 2021). In most developing countries, the study of how employees react towards these structures and how they perform under these structures can show how important it really is for organizations to implement the correct structure for the specific environment the organization is working in. The more layers in a firm, the more complex the structure of the organization, the more complex the structure, the more difficult coordination and integration of organization members become. The recent trend towards flatter organizations is a tacit acknowledgment that complexity will influence the flexibility, and can frustrate an organization's ability to compete in dynamic environment (Nahm, Vonderembse & Koufteros, 2003 in Nosike, et al, 2021). Lesser layer in organizational hierarchy facilitate decision making. The ease of decision-making refers in the operation who are more likely to know the actual situation that necessitated the decision.

Leadership style

Leadership style is the style a leader takes in his or her interaction with subordinates, toward influencing attainment of organizational goals. There are four types of leader behaviors: the directive autocrat, the permissive autocrat, the directive democrat and the permissive democrat (Lin, 2003 in Nidadhavalu, 2018). Leadership style involves the way in which the leader influences his followers. It includes the types of control leaders' exercise in a group and their behavior towards group members (Ushie, Agba, Agba & Chime, 2010). Transformational leadership is what motivates employees to achieve more rather than what was originally planned. It means to go beyond expectations. Transformational leadership has high impact on followers and changes their attitude and beliefs for their own interest and at the same time this change in behavior benefits the organization (Asgha and Oino, 2018). Transformational leadership focuses on promoting development and strategic thinking in the organization and carries on the change process more effectively than others. Transformational leaders take care of others and never discriminate on the basis of race, color, sex, religion, age or social class. Transactional leadership is based on leader-follower exchange where the follower acts according to the instructions of leader and leader rewards the followers. The main thing of exchange is compensation which may be positive or negative. Positive like praise or recognition if follower obeys the instructions of leader and negative like disciplinary actions if follower neglects to obey leader's instructions, Transactional leaders maintain stability in the organization by recognizing followers' needs and desires and then clarifying how those needs and desires will be

satisfied in exchange for meeting specified objectives or performing certain duties. A leader who avoids or does not interfere with the work assignments or may entirely avoid responsibilities and does not guide or support the followers can be considered as a laissez-faire style of leader. This leader's style is compared with dissatisfaction, unproductiveness, and ineffectiveness. Laissez-faire style leaders maintain a hands-off approach and are rarely involved in decision-making and contributing any guidance and direction. This leadership style enables the subordinates to make their own decisions, as the leader exhibits no real authority. The leader only responds to questions and provides information or gives support to the group. The subordinates of laissez-faire leaders have to seek other sources to assist them in making final decisions (Nidadhavolu, 2018).

Employee Satisfaction

Employee satisfaction is one of the most frequently investigated variables in organizational culture, behavior and other occupational phenomena, ranging from job design to supervision because it encapsulates an employee's feeling about his/ her job and is influenced by several internal and external factors, like the individual's values, principles, personality and expectations and the job's nature, the opportunities provided (Gupta & Reeta, 2019). Rival (2009) in Syahrums, Brahmasari & Nugroho (2016) view satisfaction is an evaluation that describes an individual feeling happy or disgruntled attitude in work and each individual has a level of satisfaction varies according to the value system that applies to him. The higher the assessment of the perceived activities in accordance with the wishes of individuals, the higher the satisfaction with the activity. Employee satisfaction is the satisfaction of employees with their jobs and leaders (Pongton & Suntrayuth, 2019). Gosain & Sinha (2021) visualize that employees who are highly satisfied with the organizational climate have more passion for their work and the higher the satisfaction with organizational Climate, the higher the employee's organizational commitment.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories; Person-Environment Fit Theory. Person-environment fit theory arises from Kurt Lewin's equation of behavior, which states that behavior is dependent on the person as well as the environment. The concept of P-E fit emerged from the interactionist backdrop, emphasizing the importance of fit between a person and a work environment and has been defined as the "compatibility between an individual and a work environment that occurs when their characteristics are well matched (Yun, 2012). The freedom of individuals to choose their goals, activities, and relationships, asking themselves whether their environment (opportunities, demands, social context) is a perfect fit because of suboptimal choices and individuals and their environments changes are likely to take place over time. The Nigerian dynamic economy and related changes in organizations force employees into situations that they may not have desired at first, which may cause an increase in misfits at work and people exert substantial time and effort in seeking a suitable job, that is, a job that matches their qualifications, fulfills their specific needs, and meets their goals and values (Vianen, 2018).

Person-environment fit theories highlight the importance of individuals' need satisfactions and motivations because individuals seek environments in which they are able to satisfy their needs while attempting to avoid environments that might limit their ability to satisfy these needs and includes two distinct types which are; complementary and supplementary types of fit. Complementary fit occurs when a "weakness or need of the environment is offset by the strength of the individual, and vice versa" or when fulfillment of the demands of a task or job require certain skills and abilities, referred to as demands-abilities (DA) fit, or when the wants and needs of an individual are provided and fulfilled by the environment, referred to as needs-supplies (NS) fit. Supplementary fit exists when a person possesses similar or matching characteristics to the environment and is most often represented by examining value congruence or is seen as an

enduring and guiding principle that organizes people's attitudes, emotions, and behaviors, and typically endure across time and situations (Troster, 2015).

Person environment Fit theories are based on three core principles. First, fit theories claim that fit is a more powerful predictor of individual outcomes (e.g., job satisfaction) than either of its components (the person and the environment) alone. Second, fit theory proposes that outcomes are most optimal when personal attributes (e.g., needs, abilities, values) and environmental attributes (e.g., supplies, demands, values) are compatible regardless of the level of these attributes. That is, individuals with low, medium, and high attributes are expected to respond similarly to situations of fit. Third, fit theories postulate that discrepancies between personal and environmental attributes (misfits) reduce positive outcomes irrespective of the direction of the discrepancies. That is, individuals with low, medium, and high attributes are assumed to respond similarly negatively to comparable levels of experienced deficiency (the environment offers less than the individual needs) and excess (the environment offers more than the individual needs). (Vianen, 2018).

The relationship of this theory to this study is that pharmaceutical industries must establish and maintain "a good fit" between people and their jobs because some individuals are compatible with their organization while others have difficulties with being compatible with the organization because a person who has hard time working in an organization may be easily compatible with tasks and people in other organizations. In other words, due to the substantial amount of resources when recruiting new employees, it is crucial for management of pharmaceutical industries to ensure that these new hires align with the environment they thrust in.

Empirical Review

Nosike (2023) examined the effect of participative leadership style on employee productivity in pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Data were analyzed and hypothesis was tested with regression analysis. The result shows that participative leadership, has a positive significant effect on employee productivity in pharmaceutical companies in Enugu State, Nigeria, while transactional leadership style has a positive but not statistically significant relationship. The researcher proposed that corporation should involve its employees in decision making so that they are active in carrying out their assigned duties and are a part of the organization's success.

Halfdansen (2022) investigated the relationship between organizational climate, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment and readiness for change. The study was part of a larger collaboration project between the Norwegian Police University College and the Department of Psychology at the University of Oslo. The sample consisted of employees in the Norwegian Police (N=622). The hypotheses were analyzed through structural equation modelling on already existing data material. The analysis revealed two partial mediations of the human relations climate and the open systems climate on readiness for change through organizational commitment. The proposed model indicated that the open systems climate and organizational commitment were particularly important in promoting readiness for change, contributing to a greater theoretical understanding of how readiness for change can be enhanced. The study also provides practical implications, suggesting that organizations that wish to successfully implement change, should create an environment of change that produces organizational commitment. The findings provide an appealing basis for future research.

Sanchez (2022) examined the influence of professional commitment and organizational climate on the work engagement of employees in the Department of Education. The study employed a quantitative, non-experimental design using a correlational technique. The respondents were the public school non-teaching personnel of the Davao de Oro Division. Mean, Pearson-r, and Regression Analysis were used to determine the study's findings. Moreover, adapted survey questionnaires were used for professional commitment, organizational climate, and work

engagement. Results revealed that the level of professional commitment is very high, the level of organizational climate is very high, and the level of work engagement among non-teaching personnel is very high. Further, there were significant relationships between professional commitment and work engagement and between organizational climate and work engagement. In its singular capacity, among professional commitment and organizational climate, organizational climate best influences the work engagement having the highest beta coefficient. However, professional commitment can also influence the working competence but with the support of other variables.

Rožman & Štrukelj (2021) investigated the effect of organisational climate components and their impact on work engagement of employees in medium-sized organisations. The purpose of this article is to present research on the importance of requisitely holistically selected organisational climate components and to determine their impact on work engagement of employees in 626 medium-sized organisations in Slovenia, the EU. The quantitative research is based on the implementation of an exploratory factor analysis, a simple linear regression analysis and the CFA 6-factor solution for validity purposes. Based on the research results, we confirmed the hypothesis that organizational climate components leadership, employee relations, employee commitment, employee satisfaction and employee motivation have a significant positive impact on work engagement of employees in medium-sized organisations. The results help users to better understand the importance of organisational climate in the Slovenian organisations. It concluded that successful organisations should realize the importance of organisational climate components, which enhance job performance and work engagement. Thus, they must fully master all of the employee-related processes of the organisation.

Girsang & Nasution (2021) examined the effect of organizational Climate and Doctor's Works Satisfaction. This study aims to analyze the relationship of organizational climate including organizational structure, organizational standards, responsibilities, rewards, organizational support, and commitment to doctor's job satisfaction. This research is a quantitative research with a descriptive analytic approach. From the population of 121 doctors respondents were taken as many as 56 respondents. The research instrument was a questionnaire that has been arranged according to variables and has been tested for validity and reliability. Data analysis used univariate, bivariate analysis with Pearson product moment correlation. The results showed that organizational structure, organizational standards, responsibilities, rewards, organizational support and commitment were related to doctor job satisfaction with $p < 0.005$. Multivariate analysis with multiple linear regression tests obtained coefficient values of organizational structure (0.420), organizational standards (0.533), responsibilities (0.465), awards (0.759), organizational support (0.384) and commitment (0.374). The most dominant variable related to doctor job satisfaction was appreciation (0.759). It recommended that satisfaction through increasing organizational climate dimensions such as establishing doctor's SOP based on indicators of clarity of the right task, giving trust, regular supervisors doing assessments, giving appropriate workload awards, increasing teamwork and involving more doctors as part of the unit his place of duty.

Banureka, Pooja & Kanna (2021) examined how organizational environment affects employee commitment and job satisfaction in a manufacturing industry. This study was undertaken to know about the employee commitment and job satisfaction in the organization, to determine the factors influencing the employee commitment and job satisfaction, to identify the benefits of employee commitment and job satisfaction, to understand the attitude of employees, to understand about employee job satisfaction level, to know about employees' commitment and their opinions towards work. Descriptive research design is used for this project. The statistical tools used were regression, chi square, independent t-test, one-way Anova were used for analysis. The result of the findings were that employee commitment and job satisfaction are influenced by the organizational climate. It concluded that the key is to increase employee

performance within the organization as human capital is by far the most valuable asset that can sustain an organization's long-term viability.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. One of the advantages of using survey research is that it allows the collection of a large amount of data from a sizeable population in a highly economical way. In addition, survey research gives more control for the research process. This study was conducted in South-East, Nigeria. South-East, Nigeria consists of five states; Anambra, Enugu, Abia, Imo, and Ebonyi. The study made use of primary and secondary sources of data. The primary sources of data include the questionnaire, while the secondary sources of data include the journals, magazines, textbooks, and internet. The questionnaire was structured into first and second parts. Pharmaceutical industry in this study was used and the population drawn was 2087. The sample size for the study was determined using Borg and Gall (1973) TO obtain a sample size of 400

The research instrument used for the study was the questionnaire. The questionnaire was subjected to content and face validity. The reliability of the questionnaire used for data collection was tested. An instrument is said to be reliable if it measures consistently what it set out to measure. The data generated were analyzed using simple percentages. Multiple regression was used to test the hypotheses formulated exclusively for this study. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The presentation and analysis of data collected from the population under study through questionnaire. Four hundred copies of the questionnaire (400) were distributed to the selected pharmaceutical firms under study. Twenty-six (26) copies representing 7% of the questionnaires did not respond, twenty-four (24) copies representing 6% of the total questionnaire administered were not properly completed and could not be used for any manner of analysis. Three hundred and fifty (350) copies representing 88% of the population selected for the study were duly completed and used for the analysis. The analysis was based on frequency distribution and simple percentages. This table is the analysis of the socio-economic profile of the selected Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 4.1.1 Demographic Data of Respondents

Item	Range (years)	Frequency	Percentage
Males		185	53
Female		165	47
Total		350	100
Age:	20-29	80	23
	30-39	60	17
	40-49	102	29
	50-59	64	18
	60 & above	44	13
Total		350	100
Educational qualification	GCE/WASCE	58	17
	OND/NCE	118	34
	HND/B.Sc	116	33
	M.Sc/MBA/Others	58	16
Total		350	100
Work Experience	>1 year	76	22
	1-5years	62	18
	6-10years	147	42
	10years & above	65	18
Total		350	100
Job positions	Top management/owners	36	10
	Middle management	45	14
	Operational staff	47	13
Total		222	63
Total		350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1.1 indicates that 185 staff are males while 165 are females. This is presented by 53% and 47% respectively. Concerning the age, majority is within the age range of 40-49 and 20-39 years. These are represented by 102 respondents and 29% and 80 respondents representing 23%. The minorities are within the range of 30-99 years represented by 60 and 17%, 60 & above represented by 44 and 13%, and 50-59 years and above represented by 64 and 18%. Concerning the educational qualification, majority of the workers shows that they obtained tertiary educational qualification. This is represented by 118 respondents and 34%. About work experience, 10 years and above experience is represented by 65 respondents and 18%, 6-10 years' experience and it is represented by 147 respondents and 42%, greater than 1 year is represented by 76 and 22% and 1-5 years represented by 62 and 18%. About job position, majority are operational staff and is represented by 222 respondents and 63%.

Research Question 1: *To what extent does communication affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?*

Responses on communication and employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?

	SCALE					TOTAL
	SA,	A,	U,	D,	SD	
The level of employee satisfaction is directly related to how well their roles and duties are communicated to them.	197 (56)	104 (30)	17 (5)	19 (5)	13 (4)	350 (100)
Through communication, the roles and responsibilities of an employee to work are implemented properly and with full dedication.	207 (59)	87 (25)	14 (4)	26 (7)	16 (5)	350 (100)
Ineffective communication can lead to job dissatisfaction among workers due to the managers' weaknesses and obstacles in their communication	198 (57)	104 (29)	13 (4)	16 (5)	19 (5)	350 (100)
Employees are more satisfied when they are supported by their co-workers and superiors, have an understanding of the precise role of their job.	187 (53)	99 (28)	15 (5)	24 (7)	25 (7)	350 (100)
Employee job satisfaction through communication with supervisors is a key element of communication competence because when workers are satisfied, they commit to a long-term relationship with a company.	182 (52)	141 (40)	9 (3)	4 (1)	14 (4)	350 (100)
Total	194 (55)	107 (31)	14 (4)	18 (5)	17 (5)	350 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

In table 4.1.2 five test questions were posed to determine the extent to which communication affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The first test question was to determine if the level of employee satisfaction is directly related to how well their roles and duties are communicated to them. From the responses 56% strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 5% remained undecided, 5% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed. The second test was posed to ascertain if through communication, the roles and responsibilities of an employee to work are implemented properly and with full dedication. From the responses 59% strongly agreed, 29% agreed, 4% remained undecided, 7% disagreed and 5% disagreed.

The third test question was to ascertain if ineffective communication can lead to job dissatisfaction among workers due to the managers' weaknesses and obstacles in their communication. From the responses 57% strongly agreed, 29% agreed, 4% remained undecided, 5% disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed. The fourth test question sought out to determine if employees are more satisfied when they are supported by their co-workers and superiors, have an understanding of the precise role of their job. From the responses 53% strongly agreed, 28% agreed, 5% remained undecided, 7% disagreed and 7% strongly disagreed. The fifth test question sought out to determine if employee job satisfaction through communication with

supervisors is a key element of communication competence because when workers are satisfied, they commit to a long-term relationship with a company. From the responses 52% strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 3% remained undecided, 1% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed.

Research Question 2: *To what degree does leadership style influence employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?*

Table: Responses on leadership style and employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria

	SCALE					TOTAL
	SA,	A,	U,	D,	SD	
Leadership styles have a great influence on employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment	132 (38)	161 (46)	27 (8)	19 (5)	11 (3)	350 (100)
Various leadership styles have become one of the main of employees.	179 (51)	117 (33)	24 (7)	16 (5)	14 (4)	350 (100)
Strong leadership behavior is essential for the proper communication of information among the individual team members	148 (42)	129 (36)	37 (11)	20 (6)	16 (5)	350 (100)
The demand for leadership such as analytical, methodological problem-solving skills, for effective organizational performance.	174 (50)	102 (29)	45 (13)	14 (4)	15 (4)	350 (100)
Where good leadership skills are practiced, there is measurable growth in the organization and the employees remain satisfied	181 (52)	99 (28)	39 (11)	14 (4)	17 (5)	350 (100)
Total	163 (47)	122 (35)	33 (9)	17 (5)	15 (4)	350 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

In table above five test questions were posed to determine the degree to how leadership style influence employees' satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The first test question was to determine if leadership styles have a great influence on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment. From the responses 38% strongly agreed, 46% agreed, 8% remained undecided, 5% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed. The second test was posed to ascertain if various leadership styles has become one of the main triggers in improving the levels of performance and loyalty of employee. From the responses 51% strongly agreed, 33% agreed, 7% remained undecided, 5% disagreed and 4% disagreed.

The third test question sought out to determine if strong leadership behavior is essential for the proper communication of information between the individual team members. From the responses 42% strongly agreed, 36% agreed, 11% remained undecided, 6% disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed. The fourth test question was to ascertain if the demand for leadership such as analytical, methodological problem-solving skills, objective thinking, enquiring mind, communication and interpersonal skills, creativity, strong IT and numeracy skills in the pharmaceutical industries have become significant in ensuring effective organizational performance. From the responses 50% strongly agreed, 29% agreed, 13% remained undecided, 4% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed. The fifth test question sought out to determine if where good leadership skills are practiced, there is measurable growth in the organization and

the employees remain satisfied. From the responses 52% strongly agreed, 28% agreed, 11% remained undecided, 4% disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed.

The table shows that 47% of the respondents on the average strongly agreed with the Statement of the items, 35% agreed, 9% were undecided, 5% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed. Highlight of the statement of the items shows that leadership style influence employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does organisational structure affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria?*

Responses on organizational structure and employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

	SCALE					TOTAL
	SA,	A,	U,	D,	SD	
Poor organisation structure facilitates poor performance which restricts individual growth	132 (38)	161 (46)	27 (8)	19 (5)	11 (3)	350 (100)
Organizational structure reduces ambiguity for an employee	169 (48)	107 (30)	14 (4)	46 (13)	14 (4)	350 (100)
Organisational structure affects their attitudes to work and equally motivates employees to higher performance	158 (45)	129 (37)	27 (8)	20 (6)	16 (4)	350 (100)
The survival rate and high performance of every organization is highly dependent on the extent to which its structure matches with the technology adopted	184 (52)	122 (35)	15 (4)	14 (4)	15 (4)	350 (100)
Good organizational structure does not only increase organizational performance	171 (49)	119 (34)	19 (5)	24 (7)	17 (5)	335 (100)
Total	163 (45)	128 (38)	20 (6)	25 (7)	15 (4)	350 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

In table above last questions were posed to determine the extent to which organisational structure affect employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria. The first test question was to determine if poor organisation structure facilitates poor performance which restricts individual growth. From the responses 38% strongly agreed, 46% agreed, 8% remained undecided, 5% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed. The second test was posed to ascertain if organizational structure reduces ambiguity for an employee and clarifies problems such as what the employee is supposed to do, how the employee is supposed to do it, who the employee reports to, who the employee should meet in the event of problems. From the responses, 48% strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 4% remained undecided, 13% disagreed and 4% disagreed.

The third test question sought out to determine if organisational structure affects their attitudes to work and equally motivates employees to higher performance. From the responses 45% strongly agreed, 37% agreed, 8% remained undecided, 6% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed. The fourth test question was to ascertain if the survival rate and high performance of every organization is highly dependent on the extent to which its structure matches with the technology adopted and the ability of the organization to respond to changes in technology. From the responses 52% strongly agreed, 35% agreed, 4% remained undecided, 4% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed. The fifth test question sought out to determine if good organizational

structure does not only increase organizational performance but it has positive and significant influence on employee performances in every system. From the responses 49% strongly agreed, 34% agreed, 5% remained undecided, 7% disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed.

Regression Results

The regression results are presented in the tables below;

Table: Summary of Regression Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	of Durbin-Watson
1	.840 ^a	.706	.703	1.867	1.704

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Leadership Style, Organizational structure
- b. Dependent Variable: Employee Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above shows a summary of the regression result. The R square (R²) value of 0.706 indicates that 70.6 percent of the variations in employee satisfaction are explained by variations in communication, leadership style, conflict management, organizational structure and reward management. Similarly, R square adjusted value of 0.703 indicates that 70.3% of variation in the dependent variable is accounted by variation in the independent variable, all things been equal. The Durbin-Watson statistics which is employed to check for autocorrelation recorded 1.704 as its value which is within the acceptable threshold. This shows that the variables used in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications.

Table: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4704.657	5	940.931	269.822	.000 ^a
	Residual	1959.822	562	3.487		
	Total	6664.479	567			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Leadership Style, Organizational structure, Dependent Variable: Employee Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Version 21

Table above indicates that the F-test which tests the overall significance of the model recorded a value of 269.822 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significant. This indicates that communication, leadership style, conflict management, organizational structure and reward management can collectively explain the variations in employee satisfaction. This indicates that organizational climate has a significant effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Testing of Hypotheses

Three hypotheses were formulated for the study and the variables relating to the hypotheses were measured with multiple items which were consolidated through scale summation before using them to test the hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested using t and sig value in the coefficient of the regression result. The results are presented in the table below.

Coefficients of the Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	13.024	1.149		11.335	.000
Communication	.014	.038	.011	2.361	.000
Leadership style	.089	.038	.148	2.322	.000
Organizational Structure	.317	.049	.673	6.450	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee satisfaction

Source: SPSS Version 23

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: Communication has no significant influence on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Communication has a significant influence on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Communication recorded a Beta Coefficients of .011, t-statistics value of 2.361 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, communication has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Leadership style has no significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria

H₁: Leadership style has a significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria

Leadership style recorded a Beta Coefficients of .148; t-statistics value of 2.322 with an alpha value of 0.001 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This implies that leadership style has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis Four

Ho: Organisational structure has no significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

H₁: Organisational structure has a significant effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Organisational structure recorded a Beta Coefficients of .673 with t-statistic value of 6.450 and probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This implies that organisational structure has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The major findings of the research were summarized below:

1. Communication has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria with t-value (2.361) and p.value (0.000).
2. Leadership style has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria with t-value (2.322) and p.value (0.001).

3. Organisational structure has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction in Pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria with t-value (6.450) and p.value (0.000).

CONCLUSION

Organizational climate is a vast and growing subject. The role of a conducive organization climate cannot be over emphasized. For organizations to survive and outdo their competitors, they must continually seek to improve their performance. This is done through, having a fair reward and high level of autonomy in organisation where the employees are allowed to use their initiative in performing their job. Organisations with a good communication channel and organizational structure helps boost employee performance. Also, the type of leadership style used in an organization creates a unique and positive organisational climate as it is one of the best and simplest ways to get employees committed within an organisation. From the findings of the analysis, this study concluded that organizational culture has a positive effect on employee satisfaction in pharmaceutical firms in South-East, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Management of pharmaceutical firms should provide the right tools for their employees to communicate effectively such as instant message platforms, be open and transparent, organize team-building activities and facilitate frequent feedback.
2. Organizations should identify or detect the type of leadership style to implement to get optimal positive and high performance and morale from its employees.
3. Pharmaceutical firms should make sure that their hierarchy fits with the company's purpose, objectives and goals. They should also build ownership and accountability at all levels of the organisations.

REFERENCES

- Addassi, M.A. (2021). "Essence of Leadership in the Pharmaceutical Firms". Arab Journal for Scientific Publishing (Ajsp) Issn: 2663-5798.
- Agung, A.A.P. & Widyani, A.A.D. (2022). Effect of Organizational Climate and Competence on Employee Organizational Commitment with Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable at Bali Mandara Hospital. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis Issn (Print): 2643-9840, Issn(Online): 2643-9875 Volume 05 Issue 08 August 2022
- Aljehani, G.A. & Batool, N. (2021). Study of Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction among Employees of Private Companies in Jeddah-- Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology 18(14), 314-324. Issn 1567-214x
- Aminu, Z.A. (2020). Organizational Climate and Employee Job Satisfaction in British American Tobacco, Abuja. In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirments for the Award of Bachelor of Science Degree in Business Management, Department Of Business Management, Faculty Of Management And Social Science, Baze University, Abuja
- Banureka, R., Pooja, N. & Aswin Kanna .G.S. (2021). Influence of Organisational Climate on Employee Commitment and Job Satisfaction at a Manufacturing Firm in Chennai. Annals Of R.S.C.B., Issn: 1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue 6, 2021, Pages. 1643-1654. Received 25 April 2021; Accepted 08 May 2021.
- Boro, M. (2021). Organisational Climate and Job Satisfaction of Faculty Members in Higher Education: A Study on Bodoland University, Assam, India. *Journal Homepage: - Www.Journalijar.Com Article*
- Desa, N.M., Asaari, H.M. Razak, A.A. & Jabar, N.D. (2020).Communication And Job Satisfaction Among Workers in The Department Of Trade Union Affairs In The

Northern State Of Malaysia european Scientific Journal October 2019 Edition Vol.15, No.28 Issn: 1857 – 7881

- Djordjevic, B., Milanovic, S. & Stankovic, J. (2021). The Influence of Communication Satisfaction on Job Satisfaction - The Case of Employees in the Republic of Serbia. *Economic Horizons*, May - August 2021, Volume 23, Number 2, 165 - 178 Udc: 33 Issn: 1450-863 X.
- Eena (2019). The Relationship between Leadership Styles and Organizational Commitment of Sales Employees in Pharmaceutical Sector. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)* www.jetir.org
- Ependi, N., Purnomo, D. & Siswandi. (2020). The Influence Of Organizational Climate And Organizational Commitment To Turnover Intension Of Employees Of Pt Salah Satu Branch Of Bank Bumn *International Journal Of Economics, Business And Accounting Research (Ijebbar)* Peer Reviewed – International Journal Vol-, Issue-, 2020 (Ijebbar) E-Issn: 2614-1280 P-Issn 2622-4771 <https://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/ijebbar>
- Gosain, C. & Sinha, S. (2021). “Influence of Organizational Climate on Employees’ Commitment and Job Satisfaction”. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (Ijcr)* www.ijcr.org. Ijcr | Volume 9, Issue 3 March 2021 | Issn: 2320-2882.
- Gupta, V.K. & Reeta, (2019). Relation between Organizational Climate and Employee Job Satisfaction in Banking Industry. *International Journal Of Trade & Commerce-Iiartc January-June 2019, Volume 8, No. 1 Pp. 34-43*
- Halfdansen (2022). The Relationship between Organizational Climate, Perceived Organizational Support, Organizational Commitment and Readiness for Change. Master Thesis at the Department Of Psychology, University Of Oslo.
- Johny, P.R. & Pradeep, V.S. (2020). A Study on Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction: A Critical Analysis on the Personnel in Catholic Hospitals in Kerala. University, Gajraula, Amroha, Uttar Pradesh
- Jufrizen, J., & Pratiwi, S. (2021). The Effect of Organizational Climate on Employee Job Satisfaction with Work Ethics as a Moderating Variable. *Journal of International Conference Proceedings*, 9(1), 23-31.
- Kibret, B. (2020). The Effect of Organizational Climate on Employees Commitment In Case Of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia in South Addis Ababa District. A Thesis Submitted To Research And Postgraduate Office For Partial Fulfillment Of The Requirements For The Award Of Degree Of Masters Of Business Administration.
- Maja Rožman & Tjaša Štrukelj (2021). Organisational Climate Components and their Impact on Work Engagement of Employees in Medium-Sized Organisations, *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 34:1, 775-806, Doi: 10.1080/1331677x.2020.1804967
- Nosike, C.J. (2023). Participative Leadership Style and Employee Productivity in Pharmaceutical Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 4, no 1, pp 1059-1064, January 2023
- Nwonu, Agbaeze & Obi-Anike (2017). Effect of Organizational Structure on Performance of Selected Manufacturing Companies in Enugu State Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business & Management* (Issn 2321–8916).
- Odunayo, H. A. (2022). Effect of Organizational Reward System on Employee Performance in Selected Hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies* Abbreviated Key Title: Saudi J Bus Manag Stud Issn 2415-6663(Print)|Issn 2415-6671(Online) Scholars Middle East Publishers, Dubai, United Arab Emirates Journal Homepage:
- Putra, K.G.A.D. & Wayanmujiati, N. (2020). The Influence of Organizational Climate on Organizational Commitments with Work Stress as a Mediation Variables in Jimbaran

- Resort. American Journal of Humanities And Social Sciences Research (Ajhssr) E-Issn :2378-703x Volume-4, Issue-10, Pp-182-187
- Shabbir, M.S. (2021). Organizational Structure and Employee's Performance: A Study of Brewing Firms in Nigeria. American Research Journal of Business and Management Issn-2379-104. Volume 3, Issue 1, 16 Pages
- Sittisom, W. (2020). *Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction of Employees in Pharmaceutical Industry: A Case Study of Thailand*. Sys Rev Pharm 2020; 11(3): 125-133 A Multifaceted Review Journal in the Field Of Pharmacy E-Issn 0976-2779 Performance.
- Vanaja, A. & Sathyavathi, M. (2022). Organizational Climate With Regard To the Quality of Work Life at Apollo Hospital. *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Business and Management Volume 10 ~ Issue 11 (2022) Pp: 01-06*
- Yawman, M. (2020). "Organizational Climate And Job Satisfaction: A Literature Review International Journal of Current Research, 12, (02), 10013-10018.